

Discovering the gastronomic delights of Uttarakhand - Homestay experiences promoting organic and Pahadi cuisine

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Introduction: Uttarakhand is gathering the attention of a large number of tourists due to its mesmerizing natural beauty and abundance of natural resources beautiful mountains, rich culture, organic food, & diversity of people of plains and hills, also gaining popularity as homestays in the hills there they get authentic Pahadi food which is usually organic. The term organic refers to the overall system of food production by using methods and techniques which do not harm the environment. Plants, animals & human beings and avoid the use of synthetic fertilizers and pesticides and aims for high-quality products. The terms Bio and Eco are used to refer to organic products. The common phrase “The way to a man’s heart is through his stomach” simply exemplifies the delicious food prepared in Uttarakhand. These places have a lot of delicious dishes. While walking through the road up to your favourite place or while visiting Chardham Yatra, you can enjoy delicious and nutritious local cuisine, these local cuisines represent Uttarakhand in its self in Uttarakhand, you will be greeted by different aromas coming out from the homes of local people and street vendors and mostly this food is prepared on wood and charcoal. This is the unique thing about this cuisine. These cuisines are unique and also very popular among pilgrims and the people who visit for the purpose of pilgrimage. Some of these cuisines are (Mandue Ki Roti, Badi, Kandalee ka Saag, Phaanu, Bhang Ki Chutney, and Arsa). People are now more concerned about their health they are now adopting organic practices. Uttarakhand is the major producer of organic products this might be one of the reasons for tourist attraction in Uttarakhand. Uttarakhand government has initiated a plan to develop nearly 10,000 organic clusters in the mountain region and the centre has agreed in principle to allocate a budget of 1500 crore to develop 10,000 organic clusters it’s a vision of PM Modi to develop Uttarakhand as an organic state so that it can double the income of farmers by 2022, Many organic farming practices are running in Uttarakhand & there are variety of food which is originated through this practices like (Pahadi Rajma, Gahat daal, Bhatt Daal, Green

vegetables Cucumber, Lemon, fruits like Kafal, Khumani and many more). Here people are very fond of dairy products so pure dairy products are easily available here like (Milk, Buttermilk, Curd, Cheese, and Butter). Homestay is another thing which is very popular among tourists these days where tourists can live and see the social and cultural lives of local people and it will bring the tourist close to rich culture and cuisine. The state government is planning to develop 1000 individual and village clusters under the homestay scheme and villagers shall be given loans under the Veer Chandra Singh scheme it was decided to start by the end of 2015.

Objective

The objective of this research paper is mentioned in the following points-

- To show how homestays can promote organic and authentic Pahadi food and tourism in Uttarakhand.
- To show how homestays generate employment for local people moving towards metro cities.
- To show how Uttarakhand is promoting organic food and farming.

Need of the study

The aim to study this is to get knowledge of how home stays with tourism simultaneously promote organic & Pahadi food to people who are visiting for pilgrimage and other purposes in Uttarakhand and how it is generating employment opportunities for local people who are moving toward metro cities for job as Char Dham is a seasonal business which is one of the main sources of employment for locals.

Literature Reviews: The gastronomic delights of Uttarakhand and the promotion of organic and Pahadi cuisine through homestay experiences have received growing attention in recent years. This literature review will examine existing research on this topic.

This paper provides an overview of Pahadi/organic food and homestays that have been attempted in Uttarakhand state of India. The demand for organic food emerged during the 1970s. when ill effects of agrochemicals on environmental and human health were realized in the developed world. Therefore, Organic farming drew attention for its potential to produce healthy food together with environmental conservation in the developed world (Mader et al. 2002, Halde 2015) and as a new opportunity for income in food surplus developing countries like India in the beneath of Himalayas all villages of Uttarakhand like Almora, Bageshwar, Tehri, Champawat. These all villages of Uttarakhand provide the best organic food services in the hotel with all comfort and relaxation facilities. As Uttarakhand is situated under the banner of nature's lap and gateway to the Himalayas.

The Himalayas attract more and more tourists in a year, these homestays in the hilly areas provide the best comfort and food facilities with fully organic foods. Online travel company Yatra. com has signed an agreement with the Uttarakhand government to promote homestays and highlight the state's unique tourist attrac-

tions. Under the memorandum of understanding (MOU) Yatra will promote all the state tourism-approved homestays, wherein guests (travellers) can rent a room in the home of a local family or an entire house, the company said in a release the state of Uttarakhand is bestowed with rich biodiversity, splendid natural beauty and rich cultural heritage which are prime assets for the promotion of tourism in a place. However, the number of tourists visiting the state has been found to be very less mainly because of a lack of information and poor infrastructure that is required for the promotion of tourism. Due to this large number of people migrated from Uttarakhand due to a lack of resources and employment opportunities.

A study by Sharma and Thapliyal (2019) explored the impact of tourism on local cuisine and food practices in Uttarakhand. The study found that homestays have played a crucial role in promoting local cuisine and traditional food practices. Homestays have been instrumental in showcasing the diversity of Uttarakhand's culinary heritage, as well as promoting sustainable and organic farming practices. The study also highlighted the need for further research on the potential impact of homestays on local food practices and culture.

Another study by Bhardwaj (2020) focused on the impact of homestays on rural development in Uttarakhand. The study found that homestays have contributed significantly to the economic development of rural areas, as well as promoting sustainable and eco-friendly tourism. The study also highlighted the role of homestays in preserving the traditional architecture, culture, and cuisine of Uttarakhand.

In a review by Rawat and Singh (2021), the authors examined the impact of tourism on the environment and culture of Uttarakhand. The review highlighted the role of homestays in promoting sustainable tourism practices and preserving the cultural heritage of Uttarakhand. The review also emphasized the need for further research on the impact of homestays on local communities and the environment.

A study by Chandra (2018) explored the potential of rural tourism in promoting sustainable and inclusive development in Uttarakhand. The study found that homestays have played a significant role in promoting local culture and cuisine, as well as contributing to the economic development of rural areas. The study also highlighted the importance of preserving traditional knowledge and practices related to farming, food, and culture.

So, in a state with very limited employment opportunities, there is an urgent need to take necessary steps for the promotion of tourism which can generate employment opportunities for local people. There is also a need to take adequate precautions while promoting tourism in the state to minimize the negative impact of various pressure and threats to natural resources and local culture which comes along with tourism in a place. In Uttarakhand where most of the forest is with the local communities According to the 2011 census, there are 968 uninhabited villages in Uttarakhand and a total of 3.36 lakh houses are locked in the 13 districts of

Himalayan state. In 2001, Pauri had 27,205 locked houses. By 2011, the number had nearly doubled to 38,764 abandoned houses with Kot, Khaljikhhal and Ekeshwar being the worst-hit blocks.

Recipes of Uttarakhand

Phaanu Ingredients Method

Mustard oil- 1D 2 cup	Soak the Gahat daal in water overnight. If using Arhar Daal, soak for 1-2 hrs.
Garlic- 4 to 5 cloves	In the morning wash and rub the Daal in running water so that it is free of covering. Then grind it into a dry thick paste in a mixer or on a silbatta (flat stone) along with green chillies, garlic and ginger.
Ginger- 1D 2-inch piece	Place a tawa on moderate flame. put some oil and make thick pancakes (like cutlets) of daal paste use only half of the paste for this.
Green chillies -3 to 4	Mix water with remaining paste making it of pouring consistency. Heat oil in pan and add jakhiya seeds, (jeera) cumin seeds and (heeng) asafoetida. Now add gahat paste, turmeric powder, dry coriander powder and salt.
Jakhiya – 1 spoon	Cover and cook for 10 min. On slow fire, add the gahat cakes to gravy and continue simmer for another 10 min. The gravy should have pouring consistency. if thick add some more water and heat till it boils.
Cumin seeds- 1 spoon	Garnish with pure ghee and chopped coriander leaves. best served with badi and steamed rice
Asafoetida (hing) - a pinch	
Dry coriander powder- D 2 spoon	
Turmeric powder- 1D 4 spoon	
Water -3 cups 1l. Salt to taste	
2. Gahat or Kulath horse gram- 1 cup	

Baadi Ingredients Method

Kwada ka aata	
(choon ka aata)- 1-2 cup	Heat water in a pan till it boils
Water- as required	Now mix kwada aata (choon flour) in water and cook for 2 min
Ghee-1-2 spoon	Add ghee to it and serve hot with pahadi urad daal

Bhattkidaal (churdhani)

Ingredients

Bhatt daal (black bean)- 1 cup
Oil- 3 spoon
Wheat flour -1/4 cup
Cumin seed-1/2 spoon
Asafoetida hing- 2 pinch

Method

Heat oil add cumin seed and hing.
Add drained bhatt daal in oil and fry until it starts crackling. Do this on a low flame
Add wheat flour and sauté it until it turns light brown.
And a lightly roasted fragrance is emitted.
Now add all the spices along with salt and roast for 1D 2

Dried red chilli- 2
Coriander powder-1 spoon
Turmeric powder-1/4 spoon
Garam masala -1/2 spoon Salt –
according to taste

Jhangore Ki Kheer Ingredients Method

Jhangora -500 gm
Sugar- 200 gm
Milk-2 lts
Cashew nuts-50 gm
Raisins -50gm
Chironji-100 gm

minute. Add four cups of water and cook it on low flame stirring continuously once the daal changes its colour from brown to greenish-black turn the gas off. serve it with steamed rice.

Wash and soak jhangora in water for 1 hr.
Boil milk.
Add jhangora and stir well to averse lumps.
Add sugar and cook till it done.
Add kewara essence and mix well
Garnish with raisins and nuts.

Bhang ki chutney Ingredients Method

Bhang seeds -50 gms
Cumin seeds-3 gms

Lemon big- one
Salt to taste
Whole red chillies- 3 pieces

Roast bhang seeds and cumin seeds separately.
Grind red chillies, cumin seeds, and bhang seeds into a fine paste adding little water.
Squeeze lemon juice into the paste, add salt and serve.

Arsa Ingredient

Rice flour (chawal ka atta)
2 cups

Method

Butter oil (Ghee) -150grams
Resins -100 grams
Sugar/jaggery- 11/2 cups

Heat the water and dissolve the sugar in warm water. Allow the solution to cool and sieve it through a muslin cloth. Set aside.
Add the sugar solution gradually knead the rice flour into a soft dough. Place an iron frying pan (kadhai) on a moderate flame. Pour about 100 grams ghee in it. When the ghee gets moderately hot deep fry small poorie-like arsas made out of the dough. Cook each arsa till it becomes brown. Remove the flame

Organic Foods in Uttarakhand

Buransh: Most famous organic food/juice founded in Uttarakhand. Founded on the hills of the Himalayas Drink made from burans flower is simply divine, as the locals term it. Bright red similar to rose or strawberry drink with a jelly-like texture, Buransh flower juice taste is tangy and sweet. Treating guests with burans flower juice is a traditional practice in Uttarakhand, India. It is believed to refreshing, appetizer and relieves mountain sickness. Health Benefits of Buransh:

1. Buransh as anti-inflammatory
2. Buransh with pain-killing ability

3. Buransh as antioxidants.
4. Buransh is good for diabetes
5. Buransh flower juice is good for hearts.
6. Buransh flower over allergies

Kafal: Kaaphal is one of many extremely delicious wild fruits found throughout mid- Himalayan region. The fruit looks somewhat like deep-red coloured raspberries. They barely have any pulp, and have a big round seed in the centre. Since they are very refreshing to eat, they are well-liked by many Nepalese.

Hisalu: It is quite popular amongst the locals. This bright yellow-coloured fruit is abundant both in Kumaon and Garhwal regions and it tastes amazingly sweet! It ripens during March-April, is available mostly in and around Nainital, Bhimtal, and Almora and can be purchased from the fruit sellers by the roadside stalls.

Khumani (Apricot): This fleshy and juicy fruit is widely cultivated in Uttarakhand, and it is a popular fruit too. It is rich in beta-carotene, iron, potassium, and anti-oxidants and therefore a healthy choice. The bright yellow-red colour is a treat for the eyes too.

Bedu Fruit, Timla (Organic): No any chemical or pesticide, this Organic Bedu (Timla) Fruit are sourced mainly from the high rises of Uttarakhand. The cure for Cancer is in Bedu (Timla) Fruit, and anyone can eat this sweet fruit.

Pahadikakdi (cucumber): Cucumbers are made up of 95 per cent water, making them an ideal hydrating and cooling food Cucumbers contain an anti-inflammatory flavonol called fisetin that appears to play an important role in your brain health

Cucumbers also contain polyphenols called lignans, which may help to lower your risk of breast, uterine, ovarian, and prostate cancers Cucumber extract helps reduce unwanted inflammation, in part by inhibiting the activity of pro-inflammatory enzymes (including cyclo-oxygenase 2, or COX-2)

Cucumbers are low in calories and high in fibre, which makes them useful for both weight loss and digestive health

Pahadi Nimbu: This juicy fruit most cultivated nimbus of the Uttarakhand in the hills of the Himalayas,

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|--------------------------|-------------------------------|
| 1. Benefits of Nimbu: | 2. Remove digestion problems. |
| 3. Throat disorder | 4. Obesity |
| 5. Circulatory disorders | 6. Beauty aid |

Pahadi Rajma: a simple, mouth-watering & authentic recipe of Rajma from the region of Nainital. This recipe is a secret recipe given to me by a friend hailing from Nainital. It's a recipe her family and forefathers have been following for ages. so yes, it's an original recipe and hence the name.

Connecting the available Dots

Homestays and food these two simultaneously offer local products to national and international visitors adding new components to tourism and working

as an image builder for tourist destinations. Uttarakhand itself is offering local food to the tourist who visits the home stays facility too which is quite popular among tourist these days where they live with local families and enjoy their lifestyle, they seek to visit hilly areas like Uttarakhand to get a break from their busy lifestyle and for recreation and rejuvenation. Now a day's people are taking more initiative to improve their health so they are attracted toward organic foods and product. as it contains a higher level of antioxidants and less harmful chemical and also provides long-term benefits to people and the environment and it aims to control pests and diseases without harming environment, ensure that water stays clean and safe, produce nutritious healthy food and feed for animals too. Cows and buffalos are fed by this organic feed this is the reason why milk is also pure in this area. another initiative to increase tourism in Uttarakhand and improve the rural economy in the state and provide employment opportunities to locals, the Uttarakhand government has given the green signal to this scheme and in order to promote tourism and homestays in the state Uttarakhand tourism development will give free space to registered homestay. like the chowki dhani of Rajasthan Uttarakhand's homestays are becoming one among them to experience life and enjoy authentic cuisine, the culture of Uttarakhand .tourism and homestay is the key to promoting organic and local food of Uttarakhand as a tourist while visiting Char Dham and hill station of the state would taste the local fruits and food which is organic as well, through route and at that place which is also an employment booster for local people as they can earn from that on the other hand home stays can reduce migration of local people toward metro cities who move to those cities for employment. and there are some restaurants also in this state who are serving organic and Pahadi local foods to visitors to promote Pahadi cuisine among more and more people who are travelling in this state. or can say both tourism is promoting food as well as food promotes tourism.

Conclusion: From the above points that we have discussed in this research paper it is to be concluded that after analysing the topic of "Homestays in Uttarakhand can promote organic and Pahadi food tourism" it is proven with different points that the researcher has founded homestays and tourism are the key tool which can promote organic and Pahadi local food of Uttarakhand by providing them accommodation in the area of state or village with the local people where they can closely touch their culture experience their lifestyle cuisine. They serve tourists the local food of Uttarakhand in homestays and tourists also get this authentic Pahadi food at any Hill station and char Dham of the state. it also boosts employment for local people and reduces migration. the literature suggests that homestays have been instrumental in promoting organic and Pahadi cuisine, as well as contributing to the economic and sustainable development of Uttarakhand. The literature also emphasizes the need for further research on the impact of homestays on local communities, culture, and the environment.

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